

Assessment of potential health risks of pesticide residues on cut flowers

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Ornamental plants such as cut flowers are protected from pests through the application of plant protection products. This brings up the question of whether residues of active substances in plant protection products pose a hazard to the health of florists as well as consumers. The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) has reviewed literature and data of other institutions in order to assess the potential health risks of cut flowers from European production and the main export countries of such products. After reviewing available data, the Institute has reached the conclusion that cut flowers available on the German market pose no health risk to consumers. The same applies to floriculture professionals who handle cut flowers.

The full version of this BfR Opinion is available in German on
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